

AN OPEN-SOURCE CARBON-EMISSIONS SIMULATOR FOR SMART GRID CO-SIMULATION SCENARIOS

Danila Valko, Sharaf Alsharif and Deborah Tolk

R&D Division Energy
OFFIS – Institute for Information Technology
Oldenburg, Germany
E-mail: danila.valko@offis.de

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ABSTRACT

Modeling of carbon emissions and related footprints ought to be an important element in the development of smart power grids and advanced power systems. However, the necessary emissions calculations including scenario assumptions and default emission factors are usually beyond the scope of existing software solutions and are completely left to the user. In this work, we presented an open-source Python-based component that combines an emission calculation model and a database of available emission factors for a variety of fuels and geographic locations. This component can be part of a co-simulation scenario for advanced power systems, and provides dynamic calculations of the carbon footprint of the entire scenario, coupled systems or their elements.

INTRODUCTION

Decarbonizing the energy sector is vital to meet climate neutrality by 2050 in Europe and globally (UNFCCC 2015). However, accurately attributing emissions to power system components is challenging due to the interconnected nature of modern power grids where power generation depends on the technologies used, generation infrastructure distribution, penetration of renewable energy sources, local regulation, etc. This leads to certain challenges for power system developers, even at the design and modeling stage.

Modeling and simulation is an invaluable tool for power system behavior analysis, energy consumption estimation and future state prediction (Tsampasis et al. 2016). Smart grids as complex real-world systems have been traditionally simulated either through integrated or co-simulation tools (Tsampasis et al. 2016). Co-simulation is a cutting-edge approach to modeling modern smart grids that deal with such complexity (Schweiger et al. 2019), but the calculation of relevant carbon emissions within a co-simulation power system scenario is still an uncovered area with a lack of flexible tools. Emissions-

related calculations for a given smart grid modeling scenario in most open-source frameworks remain a manual task for researchers. The researcher usually needs to find data on historical carbon intensity estimates and sometimes perform preliminary calculations on their own (Graus and Worrell 2011). If the framework provides some means of automation, they are still quite modest and do not constitute a standalone dynamic model of carbon emissions.

In this work, we present an open-source Python-based component that combines a carbon emissions calculation model and a database of available emission factors for a variety of fuels and geographic locations.

This paper is organized as follows. In the next subsections, we review normative approaches to estimating carbon emissions in the energy sector, as well as related work and software. The method section presents the methodology we adapted and its implementation within a co-simulation framework. The showcase section presents a photovoltaic (PV) and wind power penetration scenario, followed by a conclusion and future work.

Estimating Carbon Emissions

In the attempt to understand and analyze the factors responsible for CO_2 emissions, in particular in the electricity production sector, researchers calculate the carbon footprints of technical systems using a general method called life cycle assessment (LCA), which is internationally accredited by ISO 14000 standards. The method is also referred to as the ‘cradle-to-grave’ approach (WEC 2004). LCA is used to analyze the cumulative environmental impacts of a process or product through all the stages of its life. It takes into account energy inputs and emission outputs throughout the whole production chain from exploration and extraction of raw materials to processing, transport and final use. However, using this method implies the necessity of decomposing the system or product into smaller elements and specifying emission parameters for each of them (IBM 2019), but this requires in-depth expert knowledge or the existence of digital twins (Arsiwala et al. 2023, Zhang et al. 2024). A globally recognized and rather simplified approach

within LCA is to use emission factors (EFs) (Roten et al. 2022), which involves characterizing the potential of a given source to emit a particular greenhouse gas. High emission factor values are associated with high emissions. Precise information on EFs is important for estimating emissions from a given system within LCA, following the guidelines provided by the *Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (IPCC), e.g. (IPCC 2006). EFs are usually expressed as the weight of a certain gas divided by a unit weight, volume, distance, or duration of the polluting activity. In addition to the IPCC recommendations, there is also a wide range of adjusted emission factors for certain production technologies and infrastructure features, see e.g. (Graus and Worrell 2011). The expanded approach considers the CO₂ emission reductions afforded by demand-side interventions in the electricity system, which are typically estimated using an assumed level of grid emissions called a ‘marginal emission factor’ (Hawkes 2010).

In addition, several sophisticated methodologies have been employed by various researchers to estimate and predict CO₂ emissions and related energy utilization (Silva 2013). These methodologies include the usage of artificial neural networks, support vector machines, auto-regressive moving average models, decision trees, Bayesian networks, and other statistical and supervised machine learning algorithms (Qader et al. 2022, Arsiwala et al. 2023, Zhang et al. 2024).

Related Work and Software

Estimating carbon footprints and modeling carbon emissions are crucial tools for predicting global climate change and conducting macroeconomic forecasts. One of the most recognized models for quantifying global CO₂ emissions from energy and processes is developed by *E3-Modelling* for the European Commission. This model, called PRIMES (see at https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/climate-strategies-targets/economic-analysis/modelling-tools-eu-analysis_en), is a partial equilibrium modeling tool that simulates energy market equilibrium in the European Union. PRIMES operates in five-year increments and is calibrated to EUROSTAT data for the years 2000 to 2015. It has been used for various macro-policy analyses, including the EU Reference Scenario 2020, the policy scenarios for Delivering the European Green Deal, the EU Climate Target Plan impact assessment, and the In-depth analysis of the EU Long-Term Strategy. However, PRIMES is not open-source and is not applicable to smart power grid scenarios.

Another prominent tool is the *Energy Policy Simulator* (EPS), a free and open-source tool developed by *Energy Innovation* (see at <https://energyinnovation.org/energy-policy-solutions-model-results>) as part of its energy policy solutions

project. EPS allows users to control numerous policies affecting energy use and emissions across different economic sectors and reports total emissions of twelve pollutants along with various economic variables. Integrated macro-level models of EPS are available for Canada, China, India, Mexico, Indonesia, Poland, Saudi Arabia, and the USA. However, this is also a macro model, which is applicable at the level of national energy policy and macroeconomic scenarios.

From a low-level perspective, modern business process modeling and simulation frameworks enable users to manually assign carbon emission and footprint factors to simulated objects and processes. For instance, *SIMUL8* (see at <https://www.simul8.com/support/help/doku.php?id=features:carbon>), a software for simulating system-level performance of production systems, allows users to assign *fixed*, *per unit*, or *per minute* footprint factors, as well as emission values for certain operational states. Similar solution as a service is provided by *IBM Planning Analytics* (IBM 2019) and allows users to measure performance against emissions KPIs. This usually requires users to have deep expert knowledge of the simulated system and its emission production during activities.

The most advanced application area for carbon footprint modeling is transportation and logistics. Various simulation models and frameworks exist for calculating the carbon emissions of specific engines (Yoda, Kimikazu et al. 2007), vehicles (e.g. <https://www.epa.gov/moves>) and traffic dynamics (Zhou et al. 2015), car manufacturing (Schub 2022), and marine logistics (O’Dwyer 2023). In contrast to the transportation sector, in the electricity and smart power grids sector, the prevalent approach is to keep carbon emission methodologies on the user side. This relies on user/researcher expertise to make necessary assumptions, choose and calculate emission factor values, and code calculations within scenarios (see, for instance, (Masta et al. 2019, Tomita et al. 2013)).

In this work, we aim to integrate carbon emission calculation simulations with a comprehensive database of default emission factors. This integration is intended to minimize user effort in preparing smart grid co-simulation scenarios and related calculations for the electricity sector.

Co-Simulation Frameworks

In complex simulation studies, such as in Cyber-Physical Energy Systems (CPES), the interaction between the different models and simulation paradigms is often high. The coupling, synchronization and orchestration of the different models in different domains is addressed by using co-simulation which was shown to be a powerful tool for studying such scenarios (Ofenloch et al. 2022). Co-simulation frameworks often have modular architecture, which means users can add new models or replace

existing ones without redeveloping the entire system. Also, they offer high interoperability, which facilitates collaboration across different domains, such as simulating both multimodal energy systems and e.g. communication layer models, market models etc. (Steinbrink et al. 2019).

Depending on the use case, there are many co-simulation frameworks available, for example HELICS, Simulink, VILLASnode and *mosaik* are found in the literature. This work introduces a simulator within the *mosaik* framework – an open source discrete time- and event-based co-simulation platform written in Python. We chose this framework because *mosaik* has an active user and developer community that provides support and resources including a bunch of models, simulators and other tools within its ecosystem.

The presented emission simulator contributes to the *mosaik* ecosystem, while the model itself can be used independently. The model calculates emissions within a smart grid co-simulation and allows for a comprehensive evaluation of environmental impacts, operational efficiency and strategic planning. It can help to gain a detailed understanding of the environmental footprint and to meet sustainability goals, by identifying major sources of emissions, analyzing energy consumption patterns and estimating the effects of different management strategies.

METHOD

Methodology and Data Sources

The general idea of calculating carbon emissions for a given power generation system is to get the most accurate emission factor (EF) possible for each connected power generation unit. This factor should take into account all emission sources directly involved in electricity generation and should depend on the operating state of the generator and the amount of power produced (P). Given that, the amount of carbon emissions during the generation time (t) for the power unit i ($i \in [1..n]$) are:

$$E_i[tCO_2eq.] = P_i[MW] \times t_i[h] \times EF_i[tCO_2eq./MWh]$$

Then the sum of the emissions for all generators (n) in the system is the total emissions as in Fig. 1:

$$E[tCO_2eq.] = \sum_{i=1}^n E_i$$

To keep the approach comprehensive, we decided to maintain a database of available emission factors, which are determined in the literature based on historical data for geographically localized energy systems, experimental estimates for a particular fuel type and generation scheme, or expert knowledge. In particular, we use the *IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories* (IPCC 2006) to obtain fuel-specific emission

Figure 1: Integrated co-simulation scenario architecture. Technically, the emission factors database is part of the developed simulator, whereas the power unit configuration profiles are on the user’s side.

factors, particularly the chapter on stationary combustion in the energy industry. These emission factors account for direct emissions from fuel combustion for electricity generation and do not account for emissions from the production and supply of the fuel to a power plant (e.g. gas transport, coal mining, liquefied natural gas production, for details, see <https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/EFDB/main.php>).

For data on carbon intensity estimates depending on a country’s energy mix, we use the *Statistical Review of World Energy* and the *European Electricity Review*, which are regularly aggregated by *OurWorldIn-Data* (OWD 2023). For Germany, we also use historical estimates of the carbon intensity of electricity developed by the *co2map.de* team (INATECH 2024). Since there can be a significant difference between consumption-based and production-based carbon emission estimates (Schäfer et al. 2020), we left the choice on the user’s side, however, the average value is set by default. All units have been converted to tons of CO₂ equivalent per megawatt-hour by default.

Implementation and Usage

The proposed solution is implemented as a standard *mosaik* time-based simulator (for details, see <https://mosaik.readthedocs.io/en/latest/scheduler.html#time-based-simulators>), which at each time step of the simulation receives power output in megawatts from each connected power unit (e.g. generator or external grid). The general architecture of our integrated solution is shown in Fig. 1.

Within the simulator, a suitable emission factor is searched using a predefined configuration dictionary. This dictionary may contain the specification of (1) the fuel used by the generator, the geographical location as

(2) country and (3) state, (6) a user-defined fixed emission factor, or (5) a user-defined calculation method. The *key* parameter (4) represents additional search specification, e.g. consumption-based or production-based factors for a certain location. The user can also scale the output by an arbitrary factor by using the coefficient option.

```

config = {
  'fuel':          'Natural Gas Liquids', #1
  'country':      'Germany', #2
  'state':        'SN', #3
  'key':          None, #4
  'method':       None, #5
  'co2_emission_factor': 0.38, #6
  'coefficient':  1.0, #scales the output
}
em = Simulator.create(num=1, **config) # sim. entity

```

The coefficient can also be used to reduce part of the emissions if it is known that part of the fuel energy is used for another purpose, e.g. to produce heat, in case of combined heat and power generation (in such a case the emissions produced not for the power grid should be subtracted (IPCC 2006)).

Within the co-simulation scenario, for each power unit of interest (e.g. generator or external grid) in the network, an emission simulator entity with the appropriate configuration should be created and connected. The same entity can be used for power units with a similar configuration. Based on this setup, the output of the simulator contains the amount of carbon emissions corresponding to the input power and related emission factors.

In addition, the developed simulator can be simply used without any co-simulation scenario definition or *mosaik* as just a Python-based key-value data source object that encapsulates carbon emission factors. In this case, the *start* parameter is used to obtain the closest historical values for a given configuration:

```

config = { 'country' : 'Norway' }
em = Simulator()
em.init(sid='Emission-0', time_resolution=1.0,
        start='2020-01-01 00:00:00', end=1)

em.get_stored_values(**config) # returns emission
                               # factors timeseries

```

Extended executable examples can be found in the *demo* folder of public repository at <https://gitlab.com/mosaik/components/energy/mosaik-emissions>.

SHOWCASE: PENETRATION OF PHOTO-VOLTAIC AND WIND POWER

To best demonstrate the capabilities of the developed solution, we used a standard benchmark power network model (Fig. 2) that comprises models of conventional power plants and loads, distributed generators, PV and wind units, OLTC transformers, and

Figure 2: The CIGRE benchmark network for *mosaik* co-simulation scenario of PV and wind power penetration (CIGRE 2021).

circuit breakers. The model is implemented on *pan-dapower* (Thurner et al. 2018) using the *SimBench* power system library (particularly CIGRE Task Force C6.04.02 (CIGRE 2021)), which is based on the European configuration of the high and medium voltage distribution networks benchmark. This configuration was chosen due to the fact that it is complex enough to model and study several phenomena which could occur in a real power system (e.g. power imbalance, frequency and voltage instability etc.) while its limited size enables the traceability of the system’s behaviour.

Using this network model, as well as stand-alone simulators of PV and wind turbines, we calculated the power flow with 15-minute time steps over 24 hours (Fig. 3), the involvement of distributed renewable energy sources to cover local consumption, and the associated carbon emission dynamics. The configuration is made for the Lower Saxony region in Germany, the conventional residential generators use diesel fuel (see detailed scenario description in <https://gitlab.com/mosaik/components/energy/mosaik-emissions>).

Fig. 3 shows the total estimated CO₂ emissions profile over one day, which resulted from the dynamic profile of solar and wind activity as well as the involvement of the conventional generation sources. The figure presents two sub-scenarios within the co-simulation framework, the first (sc. 1) with the inclusion of PV and the second (sc. 2) without it. The expected results can be seen: the presence of PV allows an additional inflow of renewable

Figure 3: PV and/or wind power penetration co-simulation results. Scenario 2 (sc. 2) is without PV deployment, scenario 1 (sc. 1, dashed line) is with certain PV capacity involved.

solar energy in the middle of the day to replace conventional sources, which reduces total carbon emissions. In the figure you can also notice the dynamics of carbon emissions when there is no power flow from renewable sources. These dynamics arise from the fact that the power received from the grid externals also generates a certain amount of emissions depending on the time of day. The advantage of our simulator is that it provides historical data on specific emission factors for a given region on an hourly scale and makes it easy to account for these realistic dynamics.

In addition to that, the simulator offers the possibility to utilize the individual emission profiles for each entity within the co-simulation framework in the context of developing more complex smart grid scenarios.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we have presented an open source tool that implements CO₂ emission calculations for a *mosaik* co-simulation scenario. It can also be used for other co-simulation frameworks as a simply key-value data source that contains carbon emission factors for different fuels and geographic locations. We have also described an adaptive showcase that covers a smart grid co-simulation scenario with PV and wind power penetration.

The method presented simplifies the complex process of calculating CO₂ emissions by abstracting certain variables, such as outside temperature and other influencing factors. Our intention was to provide an accessible and straightforward framework that aligns with the general approach approved by the IPCC for the energy industry. This framework serves as a foundational step, allowing researchers to integrate CO₂ emissions calculations into co-simulations effectively.

In the future, we plan to expand the tool with emission factors for other greenhouse gases such as methane,

ozone, nitrous oxide, and regularly update historical carbon emissions data of various geographic locations. We also encourage researchers and developers to join in the extension of the tool.

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CODE AND DATA AVAILABILITY

All data, developed components and algorithms can be found in the public repository: <https://gitlab.com/mosaik/components/energy/mosaik-emissions>

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